

D6.3: Regional Scaling Strategies

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1. Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Lost and Waste
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
ROI	Return on Investment
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
TX.X	Task X.X
WPs	Work Packages

Executive summary

This deliverable outlines strategies to support the scaling of innovations within SILLs across three macro regions: Northern, South-West, and South-East/Central Europe. The primary focus is to help SILLs **identify scalable innovations**, develop effective scaling strategies, and **connect with investors and corporates to accelerate growth**. The task includes training SILLs to assess and prioritise scalable innovations, and providing mentorship to refine their scaling plans. Key challenges to scaling, such as regional market conditions and regulatory barriers, are addressed by recommending partnerships and connecting SILLs with the right investors and corporates. Additionally, the deliverable recommends **targeted training sessions** on investor engagement, corporate partnerships, and market expansion to equip SILLs with the necessary tools for scaling.

1 Introduction

1.1 ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (OFLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1. ZeroW at a Glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2. ZeroW Approach

To reach its goals, ZeroW is divided into 11 Work Packages (WPs) with different goals, tasks and deliverables. The current deliverable is part of WP6, which aims to foster the systemic innovations that are built in the SILLs, by building capacities towards near-zero Food Loss and Waste (FLW). Importantly, WP6 aims to support T4.3 by organising concrete workshops and other types of activities, which help to (1) identify and (2) address what is needed for increasing the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) of the SILLs' solutions. This link between WP6 and WP4 is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. 3 WP6 Tasks, Deliverables, Objectives, and link with other WPs

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, and against the current document.

Table 2. Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.3. Regional Scaling Strategies	Regional Scaling strategies – to present strategies & activities to overcome scaling bottlenecks.	Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	<p>Chapter 2 outlines the background, methodology, and theoretical framework for scaling, explaining different types of scaling approaches.</p> <p>Chapter 3 focuses on the SILL-specific scaling needs assessment, using a questionnaire to analyse scaling challenges and potential, informing training and support strategies.</p> <p>Chapter 4 addresses the challenges and bottlenecks in scaling across different regions, while also identifying key success factors for overcoming these barriers.</p> <p>Chapter 5 details the scaling strategies and activities designed to stimulate investment, including training, mentoring, and connecting SILLs with investors.</p> <p>Chapter 6 covers the monitoring and evaluation process, defining the KPIs and metrics used to measure the effectiveness of these strategies.</p>
TASKS			

<p>T6.1. Innovation scale-up success factors and incentives in targeted EU regions</p>	<p>Based on T6.1 and T6.2, regional scaling strategies were determined for the 3 macro regions, and activities and partnerships to overcome bottlenecks for scaling up were be defined. This task specifically focused on actors that can invest in the SILL innovations, by (i) dedicating efforts to train SILLs to identify potential scalable innovations, (ii) mentoring and working together with the solution owners their scaling strategy/plan, (iii) identifying and promoting opportunities to connect with investors/ corporates or other entities and boost their growth.</p>	<p>Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5</p>	<p>Chapters 2 and 3 describe the background, methodology, and strategy framework development for regional scaling strategies, including the tools and approaches used to engage the SILLs.</p> <p>Chapters 4 and 5 present the key success factors, enablers, barriers, and regional differences identified by stakeholders, offering insights into scaling innovation across the different macro-regions.</p>
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1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

- **Chapter 1** introduces the objectives of the deliverable and provides an overview of the report structure. It includes a summary of the ZeroW project, mapping its outputs to the overall goals, and outlines how the deliverable fits into the broader project objectives.
- **Chapter 2** focuses on the background, methodology, and approach for scaling. It defines the types of scaling and introduces the theoretical framework underpinning the deliverable's strategy.
- **Chapter 3** details the SILL-specific scaling needs assessment, explaining how the questionnaire methodology was used to map scaling potential and support needs. It includes a comprehensive analysis of the questionnaire conducted with SILLs to assess their scaling needs, challenges, and ambitions, integrating insights from previous project findings. The results are analysed to inform training and support strategies, addressing unique challenges across the different macro-regions.
- **Chapter 4** explores the challenges and bottlenecks in scaling innovations, highlighting common barriers across regions. It delves into region-specific scaling challenges in Northern Europe, South-Western Europe, and South-Eastern/Central Europe. The chapter also identifies critical success factors for overcoming these challenges and advancing scaling efforts.
- **Chapter 5** presents the scaling strategies and activities to stimulate investment, focusing on:
 - Training, mentoring, and capacity-building activities to equip SILLs with the necessary skills for scaling.
 - Strategies for connecting SILLs with investors, corporates, and other key stakeholders, including a dedicated pitching session planned for the ZeroW Final Event.
- **Chapter 6** discusses the monitoring and evaluation of the scaling efforts, outlining the KPIs and metrics that are used to track progress and ensure the effectiveness of the scaling strategies.
- **Chapter 7** provides conclusions and future directions, summarising key insights and outlining the next steps to be taken until the submission of the final version of the deliverable.

2 Background, Methodology and Approach for Scaling

Scaling was a crucial aspect of the Horizon Europe programme, which placed a strong emphasis on maximising the impact of innovative solutions across Europe. In this context, D6.3 aimed to ensure that the SILLs developed within the ZeroW project could reach their full potential by scaling effectively across diverse European regions.

Scaling innovations was critical to realising long-term impact, and without effective scaling, innovations remained confined to small pilot projects, limiting their ability to create meaningful change at the regional, national, or European levels. Scaling ensured that successful solutions could be replicated, adapted, and expanded to new markets, sectors, and geographic areas. This process enhanced the sustainability, efficiency, and reach of the innovations, making them more impactful in solving key societal challenges like food loss and waste.

For the ZeroW project, scaling innovations developed as SILLs was vital to achieving the main goal of reducing food loss and waste across Europe. Within T6.3, the aim was to ensure that the solutions designed within the project could be adopted widely, addressing FLW at multiple levels, regional, national, and European.

The **preparatory activities for D6.3** involved a series of meetings with WP6 partners to define the scope and framework for the deliverable. Although T6.3 officially started at M29, these activities took place between months 22 and 29 of the project, focusing on laying a solid foundation for the scaling strategies to be developed.

During this period, several collaborative meetings with WP6 partners were conducted to refine the understanding of scaling in the context of innovation within the ZeroW project. These discussions centred around key scaling definitions, such as Scaling Up, Scaling Out, Scaling Down, and Scaling Deep (see 2.1). The meetings also addressed the challenges associated with each type of scaling, including resource allocation, stakeholder engagement, and policy alignment, ensuring a holistic approach to developing scaling strategies.

Another key preparatory activity involved selecting relevant literature on scaling methodologies and best practices, particularly in the context of EU-funded projects. This review helped in formulating the conceptual framework that guided the approach in D6.3. During this phase, a draft Table of Contents (ToC) for D6.3 was developed, outlining the key sections of the deliverable. This draft served as a working document, reflecting the core structure that would guide the report's content development. The ToC was shared with WP6 partners for feedback, ensuring that all relevant areas were covered.

2.1 Definition, Scaling Types & Theoretical Framework for Scaling Innovations

As the ZeroW project aimed to expand and amplify the impact of its innovative solutions, understanding the various scaling strategies became essential. These strategies, **Scaling Up, Scaling Out, Scaling Down, and Scaling Deep** offered distinct approaches to how innovations could be expanded, adapted, or contracted to achieve broader, sustainable impact. Each strategy played a specific role in ensuring that the

innovations, developed as SILLs, could be effectively scaled to achieve the overarching goal of reducing FLW at multiple levels.

Scaling Up referred to increasing the size, capacity, or reach of an innovation to address larger markets or a more significant number of users. In the context of ZeroW, scaling up involved expanding a solution's ability to handle, for example, increased volumes of food waste or to serve a broader geographic region, while maintaining its effectiveness and sustainability. This type of scaling was particularly relevant when a solution had demonstrated success in smaller-scale pilots and required additional resources, infrastructure, or investment to operate on a larger scale.

For example, in the case of **SILL 1**, which was related to a food waste monitoring system, if it successfully reduced waste in a pilot region, it could then be scaled up to work in larger cities or entire regions. The goal was to replicate and expand the impact of the innovation by increasing its coverage or integrating it into larger food systems. Scaling up required significant investment in technology, infrastructure, and workforce, as well as careful planning to ensure that the solution remained cost-effective and adaptable to larger contexts.

Scaling Out referred to the geographical or sectoral expansion of an innovation. This type of scaling was about replicating a successful solution in new areas or applying it to new sectors. For ZeroW, scaling out involved introducing SILLs to different regions, countries, or even beyond Europe, where they could address similar FLW challenges. It was not about increasing the size or intensity of a single solution, but rather about expanding the reach of the innovation to new locales, users, or applications.

For instance, **SILL 8**, which focused on waste valorisation through algae production in one European country, could have been replicated in other countries facing similar FLW challenges. Scaling out allowed the innovation to reach a broader audience, potentially influencing policies and practices in new geographical or industrial contexts, without necessarily increasing the overall complexity of the solution.

Scaling Down referred to adapting or reducing the scope of an innovation to fit smaller contexts or resource-constrained environments. It was a vital strategy when innovations had to be customised to meet the specific needs or constraints of a smaller market or a more localised community. Scaling down often involved modifying the solution to operate with fewer resources, less infrastructure, or in smaller operational settings, without sacrificing effectiveness.

In the context of EU-funded projects, scaling down might have involved taking a large-scale food recovery platform and adapting it for use in smaller rural areas, where

logistical and infrastructural constraints required a leaner, simpler version of the solution. This type of scaling was often overlooked, but it was crucial for ensuring that innovations could be applied to a variety of settings, particularly those where larger-scale implementation was not feasible due to budget, infrastructure, or capacity limitations.

Scaling Deep involved embedding an innovation into local or regional systems, making it an integral part of the community or industry. This strategy went beyond just expanding the reach or size of an innovation; it focused on increasing the depth of its impact by fostering strong relationships, institutionalising practices, and ensuring long-term sustainability. Scaling deep was about achieving systemic change and ensuring that the innovation became a part of the solution to FLW at a cultural or operational level.

For SILLs within ZeroW, scaling deep could have involved engaging local stakeholders including governments, businesses, and consumers in adopting FLW reduction practices as standard operating procedures. This strategy ensured that the innovation was not just introduced as a temporary solution but was embedded into local food systems, making it a long-term, sustainable element of regional waste management practices. Scaling deep often required ongoing training, capacity building, and community engagement to ensure that the innovation was not only adopted but also maintained and optimised over time.

2.1.1 Theoretical Framework for Scaling Innovations

To effectively monitor scaling plans for SILLs within the ZeroW project, F6S suggested applying a combination of conceptual models and theories that had been successfully used in innovation scaling during 1-1 interviews. These models guided the development of strategies that enabled the SILLs to expand, adapt, or adjust their solutions in line with regional and national contexts.

Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Everett Rogers) was considered useful for understanding how the innovations from the SILLs could spread across different regions. According to this theory, innovations moved through five stages: knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation¹.

Next, the **Business Model Innovation Framework** (Osterwalder & Pigneur), which was utilised in WP7, considered not only the innovation itself but also the business models that supported them. This framework helped assess how SILLs could adjust their business models to cater to new regional markets. This involved changes in

¹ Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.

value propositions, customer segments, cost structures, and revenue models to enhance the scalability of the solutions developed in the ZeroW project.

The **Triple Helix Model of Innovation** (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff) focused on the interplay between universities, industry, and government as the key drivers of innovation². Given the complexity of scaling innovations within the ZeroW project, the Triple Helix model guided efforts to identify and foster the right collaborations among these three pillars. As SILLs were tested in different regions, this model informed how local universities could be leveraged for research, industry players for technology adoption, and government bodies for regulatory support.

2.2 Approach to Developing Regional Scaling Strategies

Besides providing SILL-specific scaling strategies, T6.3 also aimed to group them and provide regional scaling strategies. The approach to developing regional scaling strategies was an iterative, data-driven process that integrated regional insights, SILL-specific needs, and a deep understanding of the challenges and opportunities in each region. This was achieved through 1-1 meetings between the T6.3 Lead and SILL Coordinators.

Figure 4. Regional Scaling Strategies Activities & Development Timeline

Before developing any scaling strategy, a deep understanding of the regional context was essential. This was achieved through mapping regional characteristics, such as economic factors, social factors, technological readiness, and the regulatory environment (more information in D6.1). Moreover, verifying the previously completed Stakeholder Mapping was also part of this step.

Once the regional context was understood, the next step was to identify the specific challenges and opportunities for scaling FLW solutions in each region. Each region had its own set of scaling challenges, e.g., market entry barriers, regulatory constraints, funding limitations, infrastructure gaps, etc. On the flip side, each region

² Etzkowitz, H., & Leydesdorff, L. (2000). The dynamics of innovation: from National Systems and “Mode 2” to a Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations. *Research Policy*, 29(2), 109–123.

also offered unique opportunities for scaling, such as policy alignment, private sector engagement, and stronger research and innovation ecosystems.

The next step focused on conducting a SILL-specific scaling needs assessment, which was a crucial activity in developing regional scaling strategies. To gather data directly from the SILLs and understand their unique scaling needs, two distinct activities were carried out. The first activity was the distribution of a questionnaire, which was included in that iteration of the deliverable. This questionnaire aimed to assess the current scaling strategies of the SILLs, identifying whether they had already developed a strategy or needed support in doing so, and to recognise any barriers they faced in scaling, such as limited funding, regulatory hurdles, or market entry challenges. It also identified the types of mentorship and support the SILLs required, including areas such as investor relations, access to funding, or connections to regional stakeholders. Additionally, the questionnaire explored the SILLs' openness to collaborating with other entities or regional actors to scale their solutions.

The second activity, which was included in the final version of the deliverable, involved conducting one-on-one interviews with SILL coordinators. These interviews provided deeper insights into the challenges and scaling needs of each SILL, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of the specific support required for successful scaling. The results from both activities informed the development of the regional scaling strategies.

Finally, region-specific scaling strategies were tailored to address the specific barriers and opportunities present in each region, ensuring that they were practical, actionable, and aligned with local conditions. During this step, regional scaling needs, such as the availability of funding, the maturity of market ecosystems, regulatory environments, and stakeholder engagement levels, were carefully considered. The information gathered from the SILLs also helped identify the most suitable pathways for scaling, whether through partnerships, local market entry strategies, or adapting the solutions to regional contexts. Regional scaling strategies were designed to optimise the scaling potential of each SILL, fostering both public and private sector engagement. The final regional scaling strategies were presented in the last iteration of the deliverable, reflecting the tailored approach required to effectively scale innovations across different European regions.

2.2.1 Integration of Previous Insights and Findings

The insights from the previous tasks (T6.1 and T6.2) and the inputs gathered from stakeholder workshops were essential in shaping the scaling strategies developed in D6.3. In T6.1, the stakeholder workshops were organised to validate the baseline results on Systemic Innovation Readiness Levels (SIRL) from the SILLs, as well as to gather valuable feedback on the external conditions and requirements for scaling the

innovations. These workshops provided critical input in assessing the readiness of the solutions and outlined the key factors needed to mature them for wider adoption. Additionally, the workshops facilitated the exchange of ideas between SILLs with similar or complementary objectives, creating opportunities for joint scaling efforts. For example, SILL 4 and SILL 7 were identified as complementary solutions—SILL 4's solution for processing excess fruits and vegetables helped optimise the operations of food banks, which aligned with the goal of SILL 7 to improve food bank networks. Similarly, SILL 1 and SILL 9 were grouped for a workshop due to their shared challenges in operationalising food loss and waste data and creating solutions that were compatible across regions.

The outcomes of these workshops reported in D6.1 were integrated into D6.3 by matching SILLs based on similar stakeholders, technology, and scaling needs. These matches were used to build regional scaling strategies, ensuring they were regionally relevant and based on real-world collaborations. The inputs from the workshops also helped verify common barriers and challenges that SILLs faced, such as regulatory hurdles, market entry, and resource allocation, and these insights were used to shape the tailored strategies for each region.

Furthermore, the information obtained from these workshops, combined with the analysis of scaling strategies and needs through the questionnaire and interviews with SILL coordinators, provided a comprehensive understanding of the regional contexts in which each SILL operated.

3 SILL-Specific Scaling Needs Assessment

Before identifying the specific training needed to support SILLs in scaling their innovations, a questionnaire was circulated to gather firsthand insights from each SILL Coordinator. This questionnaire helped provide a clearer picture of where each solution owner stood in terms of readiness, awareness of scaling opportunities, and the challenges they faced. The approach was grounded in real data, allowing the training, mentoring, and capacity-building efforts to be tailored to meet the unique needs of each SILL across regions. This initial step laid the groundwork for developing a targeted support framework that addressed the gaps and strengths the SILLs themselves identified.

Between M37 and M40, **1-1 interviews** were conducted with each SILL to further expand on the answers provided in the questionnaire and gain a deeper understanding of their specific scaling barriers, as well as to test theoretical frameworks explained in 2.1. These interviews provided an opportunity to explore the unique challenges each SILL faced and helped tailor their scaling strategies to align

with the methodologies suggested in the project. Moreover, collaboration took place to refine their approaches, identify key resources and support needed, and ensure that their strategies were well-equipped to scale effectively in their respective regions.

3.1 Questionnaire Methodology to Mapping Scaling Potential and Support Needs

The questionnaire aimed to achieve several key objectives to support the scaling efforts of the SILLs. One of the primary goals was to help SILLs identify scalable innovations by assessing their confidence in determining which of their innovations had the potential for growth, both in general and within their specific regions. This insight was crucial for understanding how familiar SILLs were with the scaling process and where they stood in terms of readiness, allowing the training to be better tailored and focused on the innovations with the highest potential for impact. By doing so, the SILLs could more effectively allocate their resources toward the initiatives most likely to succeed.

Another critical aim was to support SILL owners in developing practical scaling plans. The questionnaire assessed where each SILL was in terms of their scaling strategy, their understanding of funding options, and their ability to access markets. With this data, targeted mentorship was provided, addressing each SILL's unique needs whether they required help with scaling strategies, funding acquisition, or market entry. The focus was on providing practical, actionable support to help the SILLs move forward with confidence and clarity.

The questionnaire also sought to encourage regional and cross-sector partnerships, recognising collaboration as a transformative approach to overcoming scaling challenges. With questions exploring the networks of the SILLs and their willingness to collaborate, the questionnaire aimed to uncover opportunities to connect them with other entities facing similar challenges. These partnerships provided the strength needed to overcome significant obstacles such as regulatory barriers or market expansion issues, while fostering solutions that benefited all involved parties.

Additionally, the questionnaire helped identify the resources required for scaling success. Beyond developing a solid plan, scaling demanded adequate funding, infrastructure, and talent. The questionnaire highlighted the resources SILLs felt were most needed, enabling a targeted approach to capacity-building efforts that had the greatest impact. Ensuring that SILLs were well-equipped not only with knowledge but also with the practical support required for scaling was a crucial outcome of the questionnaire.

Finally, the questionnaire aimed to gather insights into the specific barriers faced by each SILL in their scaling efforts, as well as their understanding of public and private funding opportunities. It also explored their perceptions of what might have deterred investors from supporting their innovations. These insights were invaluable in identifying potential obstacles in securing funding and in developing strategies to address these issues, creating pathways to connect SILLs with potential investors or funding agencies.

Table 3. Questionnaire Questions Objective, Goal, Purpose & Challenges Addressed

Questionnaire questions	Objective/ Goal	Purpose/ Challenges Addressed	Insights Sought
Knowledge and Preparedness for Scaling			
How knowledgeable are you about scaling your innovation (generally and/or in your region)?	To assess the SILL's understanding of scaling in general and regionally, and to identify gaps in knowledge that might have required further support or training.	Understood scaling strategies, regional market dynamics, and local challenges.	To gauge each SILL's self-perception of their knowledge and identify areas where further support or training was needed.
Experience with Regional Scaling	To understand the SILL's experience with scaling their innovation in the region.	Assessed the challenges, outcomes, and lessons from previous scaling efforts.	Identified the specific regional challenges encountered, and how those experiences informed future scaling strategies.
Do you have a defined scaling strategy or plan for your innovation?	To determine if the SILL had a formal plan or strategy in place for scaling their innovation.	Understood whether the SILL had a clear and structured approach to scaling and if it needed refinement.	Identified gaps in scaling plans or confirmed if the existing strategy was sufficient for successful scaling.

What challenges do you foresee in scaling your innovation?	To identify the potential barriers that SILLs anticipated in scaling their innovations.	Gained insight into the challenges SILLs expected to encounter, such as funding, market readiness, or regulations.	Pinpointed key obstacles that needed to be addressed, helping to prioritise areas for support.
Support and Training needs			
What areas would you like support in to enhance your scaling potential?	To identify specific areas where SILLs felt they needed additional support to enhance scaling.	Understood the individual support needs of each SILL, such as funding, partnerships, or market access.	Identified priority areas for tailored support, ensuring that resources and capacity-building efforts were focused on the most impactful needs.
Do you currently receive mentorship or support from any organisation in scaling efforts?	To assess whether SILLs were receiving external support and mentorship for scaling efforts.	Identified gaps or existing mentorship that SILLs were receiving and determined if further support was needed.	Understood the level of support each SILL was receiving to determine if additional or targeted mentorship was required.
Awareness of Funding Opportunities			
Are you aware of available public funding opportunities for innovation in your region?	To assess SILLs' awareness of available public funding opportunities for innovation in their region.	Understood whether SILLs were aware of public funding sources such as government grants or innovation support programmes.	Identified knowledge gaps in available funding and determined if additional guidance or training was needed.

Are you aware of private investment options (e.g., venture capital, corporate partnerships) in your region?	To assess SILLs' awareness of private investment options available to support scaling.	Understood SILLs' familiarity with private funding sources, such as venture capital, angel investors, or corporate partnerships.	Identified gaps in awareness of private investors and assessed the need for connections or investment readiness support.
Interest in Investor Connections			
Are you interested in connecting with potential investors and funding agencies?	To evaluate SILLs' openness and readiness to engage with investors and funding agencies.	Assessed the SILLs' willingness to approach potential investors and funding agencies, understanding their level of readiness.	Identified those ready to build relationships with investors and those who needed further preparation or guidance.
If yes, what type of investors would be of interest?	To identify the specific types of investors SILLs were most interested in engaging with.	Understood the SILLs' preferences for particular investors (e.g., venture capital, angel investors, or corporate partners).	Determined which investor categories aligned with the SILLs' needs and scaling goals.
Regional Insights			
How familiar are you with market conditions in other regions that could be relevant to	To assess the SILLs' understanding of market conditions in regions outside their region.	Understood how well SILLs were informed about potential markets for expansion	Identified the need for targeted market research training or resources to help SILLs evaluate

scaling your innovation?		beyond their region.	opportunities in new regions.
What barriers do you think are unique to scaling for your SILL?	To identify the specific challenges each SILL faced in scaling their innovation.	Uncovered unique barriers such as technology, regulations, market conditions, or organisational capacity specific to each SILL.	Provided tailored solutions and support based on common challenges.
Explain selected barriers level	To understand the severity or impact of the barriers identified by the SILL.	Assessed whether barriers were perceived as major or minor to help prioritise which challenges needed immediate attention.	Prioritised support for the most critical challenges and focused resources on overcoming significant obstacles first.
Partnership Interests			
Are you interested in forming partnerships to aid in scaling?	To assess the SILL's openness to forming partnerships for scaling their innovation.	Understood whether SILLs were seeking collaborative opportunities that could offer resources, expertise, or market access.	Identified SILLs ready to form partnerships and matched them with potential partners who aligned with their needs.
If yes, what types of partnerships would be most	To identify the specific types of partnerships that would be most	Gained insight into the SILLs' specific partnership needs, whether	Understood which types of partnerships were prioritised.

beneficial for scaling?	valuable for scaling efforts.	they needed research collaborators, distribution partners, or joint ventures.	
Would you be open to collaborating with other SILLs in your region to overcome common scaling challenges?	To assess the willingness of SILLs to collaborate with other SILLs in their region to address shared challenges.	Understood SILLs' openness to collaboration and identified opportunities to leverage regional cooperation to tackle common scaling obstacles.	Gained insight into regional collaboration potential and willingness, allowing the facilitation of partnerships.
Existing Connections and Networks			
Are you currently part of any networks or ecosystems that support innovation scaling?	To understand if SILLs had already engaged with existing networks or ecosystems that assisted with scaling their innovations.	This question aimed to identify if SILLs were leveraging support structures that could provide guidance, resources, or connections for scaling.	Identified gaps in networks or ecosystems and understood how well-connected SILLs were to scaling-support systems.
If yes, which of the following networks or ecosystems are you part of?	Gathered specific information about which networks or ecosystems SILLs were currently engaged with.	This follow-up question aimed to list and identified the specific networks or ecosystems that supported	Understood the range and diversity of networks or ecosystems SILLs were involved with, which highlighted available resources and collaboration opportunities.

		innovation scaling.	
Barriers to Investment			
In your opinion, what are the key barriers preventing private investors from supporting innovations like yours?	Identified perceived obstacles that prevented private investors from engaging with specific innovations.	This question was designed to capture the SILLs' insights on what might have been deterring private investment in their innovation.	Identified common or unique barriers SILLs faced in attracting private investment, such as risk perceptions, regulatory issues, or market readiness.
Capacity for Scaling Up			
Which of the following resources would you need most for successful scaling?	To identify the specific resources SILLs believed were most critical to successfully scaling their innovation.	This question sought to prioritise the resources that SILLs felt would have had the greatest impact on their scaling efforts, such as funding, expertise, or market access.	Determined the top priorities for resource allocation, whether it was financial support, strategic partnerships, or other vital elements needed for scaling.

3.1.1 Questionnaire Insights: Informing Training and Support Strategies

Detailed answers from the questionnaire, which provided valuable insights into the scaling challenges, needs, and ambitions of each SILL, could be found in **Appendix I: ZeroW Scaling Strategies Questionnaire Answers**. This appendix presented a comprehensive breakdown of the responses, offering a deeper understanding of the specific barriers and opportunities identified by the SILLs. These insights were crucial in shaping the support strategies and scaling frameworks discussed throughout the deliverable. Readers were encouraged to refer to this section for a more granular view of the data collected.

3.1.1.1 SILL #1 FLW Monitoring and Assessment

SILL 1, focusing on the FLW Monitoring and Assessment project, had demonstrated a good level of experience and knowledge in scaling innovations, particularly through their use of the DIH AGRIFOOD Data Space. They leveraged an extensive network of stakeholders that included farmers, supply chain actors, technology providers, academia, citizens, and policymakers. This network had enabled the adoption of digital tools like MyFarm and Farm Manager, which optimised farm operations and improved decision-making. These tools served as entry points for more advanced innovations, such as Data Spaces, which enhanced traceability and supply chain efficiency. Blockchain-based traceability systems had also been successfully implemented to address challenges around consumer trust and market access for local producers.

However, SILL 1 identified data sharing as a major challenge for scaling. Stakeholders, particularly in the agri-food sector, were often reluctant to share data due to concerns about losing competitive advantage, data misuse, and confidentiality breaches. This lack of trust and the unclear benefits of data sharing presented significant barriers. Additionally, SILL 1 wanted to receive support in understanding behavioural change strategies, particularly how other regions had managed to overcome these challenges.

SILL 1 was aware of both public and private funding opportunities, although they were not receiving mentorship or external support for scaling at the time. They were open to connecting with public funding agencies and viewed partnerships with organisations that recognised the benefits of data sharing as crucial for scaling success. They were also interested in collaborating with other SILLs through shared training programs and were involved in several innovation ecosystems, including regional hubs, industry associations, and international networks.

A key barrier to securing private investment for their innovations was the unclear return on investment (ROI) and the risk aversion of investors. To address this, SILL 1 highlighted the need for regulatory support and funding as essential resources for their scaling efforts.

3.1.1.2 SILL #2: Sustainable and Smart Packaging

SILL 2 focused on Sustainable and Smart Packaging, with a high level of expertise in packaging technologies through their reference centres, ITENE (for packaging technologies) and NOVAMONT (for materials development). However, they did not yet have a fully defined scaling strategy. Their primary challenges for scaling included

market entry barriers and regulatory hurdles, particularly related to policies on food contact and compostability certification.

SILL 2 would have benefited from developing a scaling strategy and receiving training in investor relations, as well as gaining a deeper understanding of funding opportunities and regional market conditions. They were aware of both public funding opportunities and private investment options and were interested in connecting with investors such as angel investors, venture capital, and corporate partnerships.

When it came to scaling, SILL 2 also faced stock management challenges, which were tied to how their solutions were implemented at retail or consumer levels. These challenges were critical to managing and controlling the scale of their innovations.

SILL 2 was eager to form partnerships, particularly with regional government agencies, local or international corporates, and universities/research institutions. They were also open to collaborations with other SILLs, especially in joint market entry strategies, resource sharing, and joint investor outreach.

They were part of key networks and ecosystems, including industry associations and government-supported innovation programmes, but saw unclear return on investment as a major barrier to attracting private investment. To successfully scale, they needed resources such as funding, technology/infrastructure, and strategic partnerships.

3.1.1.3 SILL #3 Wasteless Greenhouse Solutions

SILL 3 focused on Wasteless Greenhouse Solutions and possessed a moderate level of expertise in scaling, with experience in scaling digital technology solutions at both national and international levels. However, like SILL 2, they were still in the process of developing their scaling strategy.

Their primary challenges revolved around limited funding and market entry barriers, which they had yet to fully address. Interestingly, they had not identified specific areas for additional support, indicating they may have needed guidance in recognizing their scaling needs.

SILL 3 was aware of public funding opportunities but had only a limited understanding of private investment options. They were not engaged with investors and were not actively seeking investor connections at that time. However, they had expressed familiarity with market conditions outside their region and recognised that funding limitations, both regionally and broadly posed a significant challenge to their scaling efforts.

SILL 3 was not part of any partnerships or collaborations for scaling at that time, but they were open to forming partnerships. In particular, they were interested in joint investor outreach, suggesting a potential opportunity for collaboration in this area. Nevertheless, they had not yet engaged in any networks or ecosystems supporting innovation scaling.

A key barrier preventing private investors from supporting innovations in SILL 3 was the unclear return on investment. To overcome this, they needed resources such as funding and strategic partnerships to boost their scaling efforts.

3.1.1.4 SILL #4 Mobile Food Valorisation as a Service

SILL 4 focused on Mobile Food Valorisation as a Service and had moderate experience with scaling innovation. They encountered technical issues with the mobile unit they were evaluating, which led to a shift in their plans. Instead of exclusively focusing on the mobile unit, they evaluated a more versatile and flexible processing line at a fixed location. They also noted that similar mobile technologies had successfully scaled in their region and beyond, particularly in the Netherlands and Germany.

SILL 4 was still developing its scaling strategy and faced multiple challenges, including limited funding, a lack of skilled workforce, market entry barriers, competition, and regulatory hurdles. These challenges highlighted the complex environment in which they were operating, both in terms of technical capability and market conditions.

The areas where SILL 4 sought support included training in investor relations, building corporate partnerships, identifying regional market opportunities, understanding funding opportunities, and developing a scaling strategy.

While SILL 4 was aware of public funding options, their understanding of private investment options was only partial. Despite this, they were already interested in connecting with both private investors (such as angel investors and venture capital) and corporate partnerships.

SILL 4 also demonstrated familiarity with market conditions in other regions and identified three significant barriers to scaling: market competition, policy and regulatory challenges, and funding limitations. These barriers were spread across regional, national, and European levels, with regulatory hurdles representing an especially significant challenge.

Despite these obstacles, SILL 4 was open to forming partnerships to enhance its scaling potential. They saw value in joint investor outreach, shared training programmes, joint market entry strategies, and resource sharing. They would have

benefited from collaborations with local and international corporates and regional government agencies.

When asked about private investment, SILL 4 identified risk aversion among investors and unclear ROI as major deterrents. To counter these, SILL 4 emphasised the need for strategic partnerships, regulatory support, and funding to create a more attractive environment for investors.

3.1.1.5 SILL #5 Ugly Food Identification

SILL 5 focused on Ugly Food Identification and had moderate knowledge about scaling innovations. Their team had prior experience in scaling through other EU projects, though they were not currently in the process of scaling this specific innovation.

Key challenges faced by SILL 5 included regulatory hurdles and market entry barriers. These challenges were particularly significant at both the European and regional levels, as regulatory challenges tended to be complex and varied across regions. Market entry barriers were also noted, which could have indicated difficulties in breaking into established or competitive markets. To overcome these challenges, SILL 5 sought support in developing a scaling strategy and identifying regional market opportunities.

Although they were not currently receiving mentorship or other forms of support, SILL 5 was aware of public funding opportunities and private investment options such as angel investors, venture capital, and corporate partnerships. This suggested that they had a good understanding of available financial resources but might have needed further assistance in navigating these opportunities effectively.

SILL 5 expressed interest in connecting with potential investors and saw value in engaging with both public funding agencies and private investors. They also understood market conditions outside of their immediate region but were particularly hindered by policy and regulatory challenges, which they saw as the main barrier to scaling their innovation.

While SILL 5 was not currently part of any collaborative networks or partnerships, they identified a need for regulatory support and strategic partnerships. Additionally, like other SILLs, they saw unclear return on investment as a major concern for potential investors. This highlighted the need for them to develop a clear financial narrative or strategy to attract investment by demonstrating a viable path to profitability.

3.1.1.6 SILL #6 Data-Driven Production Process Control

SILL 6, which focused on Data-Driven Production Process Control, demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge when it came to scaling their innovation. Their expertise was particularly strong in two areas: food product development and algorithm development for advanced technologies such as Near-Infrared (NIR) and Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI). These capabilities were applied at a pilot scale, with ambitions to scale to industrial levels, especially for regional SMEs. However, while their innovation was progressing, it remained in the developmental phase, and the team encountered several key challenges.

One of the most significant barriers to scaling for SILL 6 was limited funding. This challenge, coupled with a lack of skilled workers, presented operational difficulties that slowed down the adoption of their technology. Furthermore, they navigated a complex regulatory landscape, which added another layer of difficulty. They also acknowledged a gap in knowledge related to the use of digital tools, which was particularly concerning for a project that aimed to apply advanced data-driven technologies at scale.

The team recognised the need for external support in several crucial areas. They were keen on developing a clear scaling strategy, which would have provided them with a roadmap for growth. Additionally, they expressed a desire for training in investor relations. Building corporate partnerships was another priority for SILL 6, and while they were aware of both public funding agencies and private investors, they had yet to fully tap into these opportunities and were looking for guidance on how best to do so.

In terms of market awareness, SILL 6 was somewhat familiar with both regional and international conditions. However, they faced significant barriers that hindered their ability to fully capitalise on market opportunities. These included funding limitations, intense market competition, and gaps in infrastructure, particularly at the regional level.

Collaboration was a crucial component of SILL 6's strategy moving forward. The team was eager to form partnerships with both local and international corporations, regional government agencies, and academic institutions. They believed that such collaborations could help address some of the scaling challenges they faced, particularly through joint market entry strategies, resource sharing, and investor outreach. SILL 6 was already part of several innovation networks, including regional hubs and international associations, which provided them with a foundation for further collaboration.

Despite their active participation in these ecosystems, SILL 6 still faced key barriers when it came to securing private investment. The team identified regulatory uncertainty as a major issue, as unclear or evolving policies created risk for potential investors. Additionally, there was concern about the unclear return on investment. Limited access to investor networks further compounded this issue, as the team might not have been reaching the right stakeholders who could provide the financial backing they needed.

3.1.1.7 SILL #7 Efficient Food Bank Networks

SILL 7, which focused on Efficient Food Bank Networks, had moderate knowledge in scaling innovation. Their primary experience involved sharing lessons learned with broader audiences, including food banks, academics, and policymakers. They already had a defined scaling strategy and faced barriers such as a lack of skilled workforce and regulatory hurdles.

Unlike other SILLs, SILL 7 had no immediate need for scaling support in typical areas like developing a scaling strategy or investor relations, as these aspects were not as relevant to their operations. They were somewhat aware of public funding options but were not familiar with private investment opportunities and had no current connections with investors.

They did recognise policy and regulatory challenges, particularly when working with volunteer organisations like food banks, which often had limited IT infrastructure. They were not currently involved in partnerships aimed at overcoming these challenges but were open to collaboration, especially through organising workshops or working with academic institutions. In terms of resources, they needed support in technology, expertise, and navigating regulatory frameworks to enhance their scaling efforts.

3.1.1.8 SILL #8 FLW Valorisation through Algae Production

SILL 8, which focused on Food Loss and Waste Valorisation through Algae Production, possessed moderate knowledge in scaling innovation. Their experience, primarily within MC Sonae, involved piloting small projects and expanding them to a national level. However, scaling this particular solution presented a significant financial challenge due to the need for additional dehydration machines across stores, requiring considerable investment. At that time, the project could expand to eight stores, but further scaling demanded more cautious planning and investment.

SILL 8 was aware of both public and private funding opportunities but had not yet connected with investors. Their primary challenges were regulatory hurdles and funding limitations. The regulatory landscape around the use of food waste for

microalgae cultivation was unclear, which complicated the certification process for microalgae biomass, even for non-food applications. This regulatory uncertainty stood as a key barrier to scaling, particularly for their partner, Allmicroalgae.

While they did not currently engage in many partnerships, they were open to collaborating with regional government agencies and participating in innovation networks. They acknowledged the need for regulatory support to address the unclear legal frameworks and believed increased visibility and awareness were crucial for overcoming scaling barriers. Their scaling efforts could have benefited from collaboration within regional innovation hubs, industry associations, and research institutions.

3.1.1.9 SILL #9 Informing and Nudging Consumers

SILL 9's innovation, which focused on consumer nudging through labels and recipe-selection tools, faced challenges in both policy alignment and access to investment and partnerships. SILL 9 was primarily involved in research and development rather than actively scaling its solutions. While SILL indicated that many of the listed challenges could apply to their work, scaling efforts were not the primary focus at the time. This highlighted a potential gap in transitioning from research to market deployment.

One of the primary difficulties mentioned was the need for their labelling system to be implemented across all groceries and products, which posed significant policy and regulatory hurdles. The solution involved developing country-specific labels and recipes, which had to be aligned with varying national regulations and market contexts. This complexity was heightened by the need to access detailed, localized information such as package sizes from supermarkets.

The SILL Coordinator mentioned challenges in building corporate partnerships, which were essential for scaling and deploying the labelling and recipe-selection tools. Moreover, there was limited access to investor networks, which may have impeded their ability to secure the necessary financial resources to scale the innovation. Regulatory support was another challenge, as SILL 9 was developing a solution that required compliance with multiple national regulations across different countries. Additionally, the respondent identified a lack of access to talent or expertise, which could have been a barrier to further developing their solution and enhancing their scaling capacity.

4 Challenges and Bottlenecks in Scaling Innovations

The questionnaire and workshops conducted as part of T6.1 offered valuable insights into the unique barriers each SILL encounters in scaling their innovations. Although

each SILL operates within a distinct domain, common challenges emerged, including policy limitations, market access difficulties, and technological constraints. The following summary presents a detailed overview of these barriers, organised by SILL, to inform the development of targeted strategies for addressing these challenges.

- SILL 1: Cross-industry data sharing is essential for mapping food loss and waste (FLW), but this requires policy support and fostering a culture of transparency across sectors.
- SILL 2: Overcoming the added cost of innovative compostable packaging that signals freshness depends on clearly communicating its economic and environmental benefits.
- SILL 3: Key priorities include identifying suitable greenhouses for the tomato quality scanning device and offering bundled solutions that integrate hardware, software, and features like pest management to attract farmers.
- SILL 4: Policy restrictions on food processing before donation create bottlenecks; expanding regulations to permit processing of donated food could significantly enhance scaling.
- SILL 5 & SILL 6: Both face challenges in initial partner implementation, SILL 5 with tomato sorting and SILL 6 with detecting salt and nitrite in poultry and require strong partnerships and impact data to support wider industry adoption.
- SILL 7: Raising stakeholder awareness and promoting adoption of tools that improve food donation and forecasting are vital to demonstrating the value of these solutions.
- SILL 8: Efforts continue to identify the best market applications for algae-based feedstock from food waste, necessitating more market research and industry networking.
- SILL 9: Consumer engagement is a major hurdle, as SILL 9 depends on CO2 impact labels and a menu planning app to reduce food waste; building user trust and motivating adoption remain critical challenges.

4.1 Common Barriers to Scaling Innovations Across Regions

When it came to regional scaling strategies, ZeroW focused on three macro-regions: Northern, South-West, and South-East/Central Europe. These insights were based on the SILLs' questionnaires and reflect their individual experiences. Each region was found to present unique opportunities and challenges for scaling SILL innovations. Northern Europe stood out for its robust infrastructure, investor networks, and market readiness, although regulatory uncertainties and strong market competition posed challenges. South-Western Europe benefited from strong public funding support and collaborative networks but continued to face regulatory complexity and

limited access to private investment. South-Eastern and Central Europe, while showing potential through EU funding opportunities and untapped markets, struggled with regulatory barriers, a lack of private investment, and workforce shortages.

As these findings were drawn from nine SILLs, they should not be considered generalisable to the broader regions.

4.1.1 Northern Europe (SILLs 4, 7, 9 - Belgium, Netherlands)

Northern Europe, particularly Belgium and the Netherlands, offered significant opportunities for scaling innovations due to their well-established investor networks. Both regions featured a strong presence of venture capitalists, angel investors, and government-backed funding programmes, which were crucial for SILLs looking to secure funding. Additionally, the innovation ecosystems in these countries were well-developed, supported by regional government agencies, local corporates, and universities. These environments fostered collaboration, helping SILLs scale their innovations by providing access to knowledge, strategic resources, and partnerships. Moreover, the infrastructure in these regions was highly conducive to scaling technologies, especially in sectors like food valorisation and mobile food processing. These countries also showed a high level of readiness to adopt sustainable innovations.

However, challenges still persisted. Regulatory barriers, particularly around emerging technologies such as food waste valorisation and mobile food processing, were a significant hurdle. SILLs, such as SILL 8 and SILL 4, faced uncertainties in regulatory frameworks that slowed down innovation adoption and complicated market entry. Additionally, market competition in these regions, both regional and global, was fierce, making differentiation crucial for success. This heightened competition, coupled with funding limitations, presented ongoing challenges for SILLs striving to scale in Northern Europe.

4.1.2 South-Western Europe (SILLs 2, 5, 6, 8 - Spain and Portugal)

South-Western Europe, specifically Spain and Portugal, presented substantial opportunities for scaling innovations in areas such as food waste management and digital production processes. These regions had seen growing interest in sustainability and innovation, with strong alignment to EU environmental goals. Public funding programmes, such as those offered by the EU, provided a solid foundation for scaling innovations in sectors like food valorisation and digital technology. Furthermore, the presence of regional innovation hubs and academic

collaborations offered access to valuable networks, which helped SILLs find cross-border and cross-sector partners to advance their scaling strategies.

However, challenges in South-Western Europe persisted, especially in the regulatory landscape. SILLs in Spain, such as SILL 5 and SILL 6, reported difficulties with navigating complex regulations, particularly in sectors like food-related innovations and digital tools. While public funding was relatively accessible, private investment remained more limited in these regions, hindering the ability to scale quickly. Funding limitations were a recurring theme, as SILLs in this region struggled to secure private investment to complement public funding. This created an imbalance that slowed down growth and scaling efforts. Additionally, while regional networks existed, the availability of investors and funding partners was less developed than in other parts of Europe, which posed a barrier to rapid scaling.

4.1.3 South-Eastern and Central Europe (SILLs 1, 3 - Slovenia, Romania, Lithuania)

In South-Eastern and Central Europe, including Slovenia, Romania, and Lithuania, there were opportunities for scaling innovations. These countries were emerging as innovation hotspots, with increasing interest in sustainable and digital solutions. The growing availability of EU funding programmes, such as Horizon Europe, offered a significant advantage for SILLs seeking to scale their innovations in these countries. These regions also had relatively untapped market potential, which worked to the advantage of SILLs that could differentiate themselves in less saturated markets. This provided room for growth, particularly for innovations in food packaging and waste valorisation, which were becoming increasingly important.

However, these regions also faced several challenges. Regulatory complexities remained an issue for the SILLs based in Slovenia and Romania, where certifications and compliance with EU standards were difficult to navigate, especially in sectors like food packaging and sustainable materials. In addition to regulatory hurdles, SILLs in these regions reported limited access to private investors. While public funding opportunities existed, there was a clear gap in private investment, which made scaling more challenging. Furthermore, the shortage of skilled workers in specialised sectors was another obstacle to scaling. Capacity-building efforts and knowledge transfer were essential to enable these SILLs to grow successfully.

4.2 Key Success Factors and Strategies for Scaling Innovations

The workshops and the questionnaire highlighted several key success factors essential for scaling innovations, which were informed by both the experiences of the SILLs and broader industry trends. These success factors, along with strategies for

overcoming common barriers, provided a practical roadmap for achieving scaling success.

One of the most critical success factors identified during the workshops was the alignment of innovations with actual market needs. Innovations that solved a pressing problem or met a clear demand were more likely to scale successfully. It was important for SILLs to continually assess the market fit of their innovations, ensuring they adapted to evolving market trends and needs. To improve market fit, SILLs were advised to conduct market research and engage with potential customers early in the scaling process. Building customer feedback loops and pilot testing refined the product to ensure it met demand. Additionally, connecting with regional or international innovation hubs provided valuable market insights and helped identify niche markets where the innovation could thrive.

Adequate funding was an important factor for scaling, as many SILLs reported challenges related to limited access to financial resources. Funding was needed for infrastructure development, talent acquisition, and market entry. Innovations without a clear funding strategy faced delays and potential failure to scale. SILLs were encouraged to explore diverse funding sources, including public grants, private investors (e.g., angel investors, venture capital), and corporate partnerships. Developing a clear and compelling value proposition for investors was essential to attract funding. Additionally, SILLs could have benefited from joint investor outreach initiatives to pool resources and reduce individual funding burdens.

Navigating complex regulatory environments was identified as a significant barrier for scaling in several sectors, particularly in industries like food production or health technologies. Uncertainty or lack of clarity in regulations hindered rapid scaling and complicated market entry. To overcome regulatory challenges, SILLs were advised to engage with legal experts and industry associations that could provide regulatory guidance. Collaborating with government agencies or innovation networks helped in advocating for clearer regulations. SILLs were also encouraged to participate in regulatory sandbox initiatives, which allowed for testing innovations under real regulatory conditions before broader market entry.

Strategic partnerships emerged as a crucial success factor for scaling innovations. Building relationships with corporates, universities, research institutions, and industry associations provided access to resources, expertise, and market opportunities that individual SILLs might not have had. Collaborations also helped share the risk and reward of scaling. SILLs were encouraged to actively seek cross-sector partnerships and regional collaborations. Leveraging networks such as regional government agencies, innovation hubs, and international networks opened new doors for scaling. Joint market entry strategies, shared resources, and

collaborative R&D accelerated the scaling process and minimised operational bottlenecks.

Access to the right talent and expertise was identified as another major factor for scaling. As SILLs expanded their operations, having skilled employees and experts in areas such as digital technologies, product development, and regulatory compliance was essential for smooth scaling. SILLs were advised to invest in training programmes for existing teams to build internal capacity and recruit experts who could support growth. They were also encouraged to explore collaborations with universities or research institutions to tap into specialised knowledge and talent. Additionally, offering attractive opportunities for talent acquisition through partnerships with innovation networks or EU-funded programmes helped SILLs overcome workforce limitations.

Scaling innovations often required significant investment in infrastructure, including production facilities, digital platforms, or supply chain logistics. Innovations that relied on complex technological solutions or physical infrastructure faced challenges in scaling if they lacked the necessary resources or partners to support them. SILLs were encouraged to focus on identifying and securing the infrastructure necessary for scaling, including production or distribution facilities. In cases where infrastructure gaps existed, exploring joint ventures or public-private partnerships helped provide the resources needed. Additionally, digital solutions or scalable technologies that required less physical infrastructure were prioritised to reduce overhead costs and increase flexibility.

A clear, actionable scaling strategy was vital for ensuring that innovations moved from pilot to large-scale deployment. Several SILLs indicated the need for guidance in developing comprehensive scaling strategies that took into account both short-term and long-term goals. SILLs were encouraged to work with mentors, consultants, or industry experts to develop tailored scaling strategies. These strategies included specific actions for market entry, customer acquisition, funding, partnerships, and regulatory compliance. Regular review and refinement of the scaling strategy, based on feedback from stakeholders and ongoing market trends, helped ensure it stayed relevant and actionable.

5 Scaling Strategies and Activities to Stimulate Investment

The goal was to connect SILLs with the right investors, corporate partners, and other key entities to accelerate their growth, access funding, and scale their innovations.

The first step in this strategy involved guiding SILLs in identifying the right investors and partners who could support their growth. This involved targeting a diverse range

of investors, from early-stage venture capitalists and impact investors to government funding bodies, each aligned with the goals and sector focus of the SILLs. Corporate partners, who might have been seeking innovative solutions or looking for joint ventures, also had to be identified. Engaging networks such as incubators, accelerators, and innovation hubs was key, as they provided valuable connections and resources.

Once the relevant investors and partners were identified, the next step was to facilitate direct connections between SILLs and these entities. This was achieved through the organisation of networking events, pitching sessions, investor matchmaking sessions, and roundtable discussions that brought together SILLs, investors, and corporate partners in a collaborative setting. Industry conferences also served as important platforms for SILLs to engage with potential backers.

Preparation was crucial for these connections to be fruitful. Therefore, SILLs needed to be trained on crafting effective, investor-focused pitches that emphasised the scalability, market potential, and social impact of their innovations. Furthermore, supporting SILLs in developing solid business plans, financial projections, and investor-ready documentation ensured that they were well-prepared when opportunities arose.

Building long-term relationships with investors was equally important. SILLs were encouraged to maintain regular communication with their investors, providing updates on progress, milestones, and challenges. Leveraging broader investor networks opened further opportunities for growth, enabling SILLs to expand their reach and secure additional funding.

Moreover, cross-sector and regional partnerships were promoted to facilitate scaling in specific markets. Identifying potential collaborations between SILLs and entities in complementary sectors helped drive innovation and opened new avenues for growth. Regional scaling challenges, such as navigating local market conditions and regulatory requirements, were overcome by connecting SILLs with regional players who had a deep understanding of these dynamics.

5.1 Training, Mentoring, and Capacity Building for Scaling Solutions

Structured training sessions and mentoring activities were deployed to help SILL teams understand and implement effective scaling strategies. The sessions focused on the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, Business Model Innovation Framework, and Triple Helix Model, equipping SILLs to tackle challenges such as resource needs, stakeholder engagement, and market dynamics.

Additionally, individual mentoring offered tailored support, refining SILL-specific scaling strategies by addressing obstacles and securing partnerships, investors, and stakeholders. Capacity-building activities further strengthened SILLs' abilities to craft compelling investor pitches and navigate both public and private funding opportunities.

5.1.1 Training Sessions & Mentoring

To identify scalable solutions aligned with the theoretical framework, structured training sessions and mentoring were implemented. The training sessions focused on equipping SILL teams with the knowledge and tools necessary to understand various scaling strategies, including Scaling Up, Scaling Out, Scaling Down, and Scaling Deep, within the context of the ZeroW project. These sessions introduced key concepts such as the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, Business Model Innovation Framework, and Triple Helix Model of Innovation, which helped SILLs identify opportunities and challenges for scaling their solutions. Additionally, the sessions provided practical guidance on evaluating the scalability of their innovations by addressing resource needs, stakeholder engagement, policy alignment, and market dynamics. Exercises were designed to assist SILLs in identifying scaling pathways tailored to their specific regional or sectoral requirements. Individual mentoring sessions then offered tailored, one-on-one support to each SILL, using iterative feedback to refine their scaling strategies. These sessions were based on insights gathered from the SILLs' questionnaire responses, allowing for a deeper exploration of their unique challenges and scaling goals. The mentoring focused on developing context-specific scaling strategies, including adapting business models using the Business Model Innovation Framework, engaging local stakeholders through collaborative approaches informed by the Triple Helix Model of Innovation, and aligning scaling strategies with the stages of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory to ensure a structured and sustainable scaling process. Moreover, the mentoring helped SILLs identify key obstacles and provided practical guidance on overcoming challenges such as securing funding, engaging with investors, expanding networks, and improving the scalability of their innovations. Emphasis was also placed on the importance of strategic partnerships, with guidance provided on how to connect with corporate partners, investors, and other key stakeholders to drive their projects forward. By the end of the mentoring process, SILLs were equipped with the knowledge and confidence needed to refine and advance their scaling strategies.

5.1.2 SILLs 1:1 Interviews and Insights

5.1.2.1 SILL 1: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the one-to-one interview with SILL 1, held on 16 April 2025, the team provided an in-depth overview of their scaling strategy, internal resources, platform development, and organisational capabilities. SILL 1's primary scaling strategy was identified as "Scaling Deep," which aimed to encourage systemic and behavioural change, particularly by building trust around data sharing with farmers, processors, and public bodies. They also planned to scale "Up" and "Out" by expanding their efforts to new regions, specifically across Slovenia and Romania. A key part of their scaling plan involved developing a data-sharing platform intended to contribute to a broader European data space for agri-food sustainability. The platform was designed to support multiple use cases, ranging from monitoring food loss to providing sustainability indicators, with a strong emphasis on interoperability and collaboration with other data-sharing initiatives.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

Several challenges were identified during the interview. The most significant barrier was the reluctance of SMEs to share data due to concerns about trust and confidentiality. While the technical backend of the platform had been developed and integrated with Slovenian and Romanian data pipelines, the user interface remained underdeveloped and required substantial improvements. Additionally, there was uncertainty about the integration of smart applications developed under WP3 into the platform, which could potentially have affected future scaling efforts.

Organisational and Governance Insights

SILL 1's internal team demonstrated high readiness for scaling, with business developers, IT experts, and community managers all contributing to the effort. They had established strong partnerships with external stakeholders, including the University of Maribor and regional digital innovation hubs. However, although a governance framework existed, it required formal documentation to clearly define roles, accountability, and operational procedures for broader scaling.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Based on the findings from the interview, several recommendations were made to enhance SILL 1's scaling efforts. It was advised that the existing governance structures be formalised into a written operational model clearly outlining roles and accountability while solidifying partnerships. The team was encouraged to accelerate the development of the platform's user experience by prioritising improvements to the user interface and conducting user testing with current stakeholders to ensure

accessibility and usefulness. Additionally, SILL 1 was urged to define a clear, transparent data-sharing strategy that included mechanisms to build trust, communication messaging, data anonymisation methods, and potential incentive models such as benchmarking or analytics feedback. The exploration of strategic spin-offs was recommended to operationalise services and ensure long-term sustainability beyond the project. Furthermore, it was necessary to clarify and resolve the technical integration issues with WP3 or, if integration proved unfeasible, to consider alternative solutions. The next steps involved finalising governance documentation, dedicating resources to enhancing the platform's UX, drafting the data-sharing strategy, and planning for post-project sustainability through the evaluation of spin-off opportunities.

5.1.2.2 SILL 2: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 2, held on 16 April 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technical readiness, organisational capacity, and market readiness. SILL 2 focused on developing a technologically complex, sustainability-oriented packaging solution, which comprised a bio-based tray, a freshness-indicating label, and a sustainable sealing film. The primary use case was for fish packaging, with Eroski identified as the initial retailer involved in trials. The team positioned themselves within two core scaling pathways: Scaling Deep, aiming to improve the quality and behavioural impact of the innovation, particularly by changing consumer understanding of freshness, food safety, and waste reduction; and Systemic Scaling, emphasising the alignment of multiple interdependent innovations (label, tray, seal) across different stakeholders within the value chain including producers, packagers, and retailers to achieve widespread adoption. Secondary relevance was attributed to scaling up, through expansion within their existing ecosystem, and scaling down, by adapting solutions for niche or local production.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

During the interview, several challenges were highlighted. In terms of technical readiness, SILL 2's solution was at Technology Readiness Level 6–7, having completed material design, prototyping, pilot-scale label production, and consumer testing. However, a critical bottleneck existed in converting large-scale label rolls into industrial-ready individual labels, which remained a manual process due to the lack of market-ready service providers willing to adapt their operations. Regarding organisational readiness, the team estimated around 70% readiness to scale, citing a strong internal consortium with defined roles and most technical skills available. Nevertheless, they lacked structured internal financial modelling and unit cost breakdowns, and no formal post-project governance strategy had been discussed. While real implementation had already commenced, with trials and food waste

reduction measurement underway, discussions about the future form of SILL 2 such as a spin-off, licensing, or joint venture had not yet been initiated. Regulatory barriers also posed significant challenges, with hurdles related to food contact material approvals and compostability standards. The lengthy approval timelines (3–4 years) for food contact materials within the EU were perceived as a major barrier to market entry, even after technical validation. Additional regulatory concerns included low consumer awareness regarding freshness-indicating packaging and uncertainty surrounding the end-of-life management of composite packaging solutions.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Based on the findings from the interview, several key recommendations were made to enhance SILL 2's scaling efforts. The team was advised to formalise a post-project operating model by initiating structured discussions among consortium members about the future of SILL 2 after ZeroW, considering options such as a spin-off, technology licensing agreements, or establishing a multi-partner cooperative for production and supply. They were encouraged to industrialise label production by engaging with smaller converters or start-ups more willing to co-develop solutions for research-stage materials, and to explore low-cost desktop conversion machinery or consider outsourcing production outside Spain if local partners proved inflexible. It was recommended that SILL 2 finalise product costing and financial viability by conducting detailed unit cost modelling for each packaging component, calculating breakeven prices, and evaluating potential business cases, supported by scenario planning workshops. To advance regulatory pathways, the team was urged to identify certified laboratories and begin pre-validation for food contact safety, assess the impact of changing food types on label re-certification requirements, and strategically plan timelines for regulatory approvals, acknowledging that these might extend beyond the project's duration. The team was also encouraged to clarify demand and customer segments by defining whether their primary customer was a packager, retailer, or technology provider, building customer personas, and using current trials with Eroski to extract insights and develop a replicable value proposition. Finally, SILL 2 was advised to evaluate a modular versus integrated solution strategy, considering a phased market entry approach since the label, tray, and seal could function independently, with the suggestion to launch individual components like the tray or label first to build credibility prior to full packaging adoption.

Figure 5. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 2

SILL 2 represented a strong example of technological innovation rooted in real consumer behaviour and sustainability. Although gaps existed in industrial readiness, financial clarity, and regulatory approvals, their commitment to quality and systems thinking positioned them well for future success. With targeted support in business modelling, governance planning, and strategic partnerships, SILL 2 had the potential to mature into a commercially viable solution with significant societal impact.

5.1.2.3 SILL 3: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 3, held on 23 April 2025, the team outlined their scaling strategy, technological readiness, and challenges. SILL 3 had been strategically positioned to scale both within its home ecosystem and into new EU markets, such as Poland and the Netherlands. This dual approach aimed to maximise market potential while leveraging existing technical validation. Although systemic scaling via partnerships and integration with public programmes had not yet become central to their strategy, early connections with public institutions and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) indicated growing openness to ecosystem-based scaling. However, two key structural barriers constrained scalability. Organisational readiness was limited as many farmers lacked digital literacy and showed significant hesitation in changing operational routines, with training and behaviour change seen as high-cost, low-immediacy investments. Additionally, infrastructure limitations were apparent in many pilot sites, particularly in rural areas, where basic utilities such as consistent electricity or broadband were lacking, making advanced AI deployment impractical without parallel investment in infrastructure.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

Several challenges were identified during the process. Market resistance was evident, as operational secrecy among greenhouse operators hindered data sharing and limited pilot participation. Funding gaps also posed a significant risk, with heavy reliance on EU grants threatening continuity beyond the project lifecycle.

Organisational readiness was low, as inadequate internal expertise among adopters delayed adoption and increased support costs. Additionally, data access gaps existed, with the absence of granular performance data preventing SILL 3 from building compelling case studies or return on investment (ROI) models.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Several strategic recommendations were made to accelerate SILL 3's scaling efforts. It was advised that a structured decision-making process around the business model be implemented, including comparative financial model simulations such as five-year projections for product, service, and hybrid models, alongside market testing through customer interviews in Lithuania, Serbia, and the Netherlands. The team was encouraged to prioritise a hybrid "hardware plus subscription" model, which would offer a one-time installation fee combined with annual access to AI model updates, analytics dashboards, and remote maintenance. This approach was expected to generate a stable revenue stream while lowering barriers to entry for price-sensitive adopters. For strategic pilot selection, the focus was recommended to be on sites with standardised infrastructure to reduce customisation costs and expedite deployment. SILL 3 was also advised to develop return-on-investment monitoring protocols during pilots, tracking metrics such as labour hours saved, water usage, and crop yield to build persuasive marketing cases.

To address data diplomacy and incentive design, overcoming the trust deficit was deemed critical. SILL 3 was encouraged to provide anonymised sector benchmarks demonstrating aggregate benefits across pilot sites and to include data ownership clauses in contracts to reassure clients about control and confidentiality. Regarding governance and legal structuring, formalising a spin-off legal entity with clear intellectual property ownership and equity structure was recommended to enable applications for additional funds, such as the EIC Accelerator or Eurostars grants.

Due diligence for private pre-seed funding in 2026 was suggested to target venture capital firms focused on digital agriculture, like the Nordic AgriTech Fund. For capacity building and training, the team was advised to develop modular, self-paced onboarding materials, including video tutorials, troubleshooting manuals, FAQs, and peer-to-peer forums. Additionally, SILL 3 was encouraged to consider launching an educational partnership with agricultural universities and vocational schools to establish a training certification path for system operators.

Critical Risks & Mitigations

Several critical risks were identified along with recommended mitigations. It was noted that over-customisation of the system to meet early adopters' specific needs

could restrict future scalability, and the solution was to enforce modular design principles and standardise non-critical components. The team recognised the risk of a funding cliff, where momentum might be lost if EU grants ended before sustainable revenue streams were established; thus, SILL 3 was advised to explore options such as convertible notes or co-development partnerships with corporates in the food supply chain. Regarding adoption barriers, it was observed that farmers might perceive the technology as a “nice-to-have” rather than an essential tool, so the team was encouraged to develop use cases that clearly demonstrated yield improvements or reductions in labour costs.

Figure 6. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 3

SILL 3 was technically ready and well-connected but faced an inflection point. Without swift decisions on its business model and go-to-market execution, the project risked stagnation after completion. By focusing on targeted pilots, encouraging data trust, and strategically formalising legal and funding structures, SILL 3 had the potential to scale across Eastern and Western Europe, catalysing systemic change in precision agriculture.

5.1.2.4 SILL 4: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 4, held on 24 April 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological readiness, and challenges. SILL 4 had focused on evaluating and implementing a modular food valorisation system using existing technologies for small-scale processing of surplus fruits and vegetables. Their core innovation lay not in technology development but in the business modelling, localisation, and integration of available technologies within mobile and stationary processing units. Their scaling strategy was largely concentrated on scaling up, with the primary focus on proving feasibility within their local region of Flanders. Changing behaviours among producers and cooperatives to embrace local valorisation was a secondary focus, representing scaling deep. The valorisation process had primarily focused on

bioenergy production, with some surplus used as animal feed and only a small portion donated. Upcycling or retaining the produce within the food chain whether as fresh or processed products had not been pursued. This reflected the situation prior to the interventions introduced by the SILL. Their long-term ambitions included scaling out by expanding to other regions such as Spain and Sweden, with potential for regional adaptation. While systemic scaling was recognised as desirable, it was considered challenging due to the need for strong partnerships and policy alignment.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

Several barriers were identified during the interview. Although SILL 4 demonstrated high technology readiness, with all components such as milling, pasteurisation, and bottling being market-ready, the main bottlenecks were not technical. Instead, they related to organisational management, business modelling, logistics, and market entry. Additionally, there were significant organisational gaps, particularly a lack of expertise in business development, marketing, and B2B sales, which hindered market access and scalability.

Know-how

Their unique contribution lay in the operational and organisational integration and flexibility to process a variety of locally available surplus feedstocks into multiple products, such as juices, purees, and smoothies, using a single unit.

Business Model Considerations

The leading model was Valorisation as a Service (VaaS), where the SILL acted as a contract processor for small producers and startups who maintained ownership of their products, or as an actor willing to invest in and operate a mobile unit or fixed hub. However, the project still lacked a formal spin-off structure, market validation, and detailed cost analysis. As a research institute, ILVO typically did not move quickly to start spin-offs or commercialise solutions. Instead, they focused on demonstrating and validating solutions, hoping that potentially successful cases would be adopted by other actors.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Several recommendations were made to accelerate SILL 4's scaling efforts. For business development, SILL 4 was advised to recruit or partner with commercialisation experts and co-develop a go-to-market strategy, potentially within a follow-up project coordinated by interested businesses with ILVO's technological support. Regarding logistics, given the challenges around collecting surplus produce,

the team was encouraged to pilot reverse logistics with farmer cooperatives or municipalities to facilitate material collection.

In terms of governance and ownership, no formal governance or spin-off structure had been planned, so it was recommended to initiate legal structuring and ownership agreements by the end of ZeroW, with ILVO expected to act as an advisor if necessary; the responsibility for structuring these agreements would lie with investors or market players interested in advancing the project. For market access, as there was no clear client pipeline for juice or puree buyers, SILL 4 was advised to identify niche markets, food service, or public procurement opportunities, contingent on the involvement of interested investors or partners.

On marketing, the team was advised to focus on B2B sales and allow clients to develop final products or brands, thereby reducing internal branding burdens. Regarding policy navigation, due to regulatory complexities with mobile units—particularly related to wastewater handling and food safety regulations—SILL 4 was encouraged to engage early with food safety authorities and consider pre-approvals for fixed hubs as an alternative to mobile units. Finally, SILL 4 was advised to finalise the business case, including costs, pricing, and break-even analysis, utilising available data from earlier testing along with a recent report on techno-economic assessment written in Dutch to assist this process.

Critical Risks & Mitigations

Several critical risks were identified during the assessment. A major constraint was the lack of clear logistics plans for collecting surplus produce, prompting the recommendation that the team pilot reverse logistics with farmer cooperatives or municipalities. Market access and client buy-in also posed challenges; without a clear client pipeline for juice or puree buyers, access to the market risked remaining limited. The team was encouraged to explore niche markets and public procurement opportunities to broaden their reach. Additionally, the absence of a formal governance structure or commercialisation lead was noted as a risk that could lead to stagnation, and SILL 4 was advised to formalise governance and develop plans for establishing a post-project entity.

Figure 7. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 4

SILL 4 demonstrated strong technical capabilities and possessed a solid foundation for scaling, especially given the local policy support and its focus on small-scale food valorisation. However, its success depended on finalising a business model, validating client demand, and establishing a dedicated entity to ensure sustainable scaling. With appropriate support in business development, logistics, and policy navigation, SILL 4 had the potential to scale effectively and drive meaningful change in the food waste reduction sector.

5.1.2.5 SILL 5: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 5, held on 24 April 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological readiness, and the challenges they faced. SILL 5 focused on developing an AI-powered sorting machine for imperfect produce, such as tomatoes, aiming to reduce food loss by enabling the commercial use of “ugly” fruits and vegetables. The AI model had been successfully tested at the pilot level, demonstrating the ability to assess attributes such as tomato shape, ripeness, and damage. Their scaling strategy encompassed systemic scaling, with the team aiming to transform value chains through collaborative partnerships, particularly with retailers and cooperatives, alongside scaling deep by seeking to change internal behaviours and perceptions across various levels of workers and management. While scaling up expanding use within existing partners and scaling out exploring new produce and regions were potential goals, these were not immediate priorities.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

The team identified several key barriers to scaling. One of the major challenges was gaining the cooperation of retailers, primarily due to concerns around data privacy and reputational risks, such as the fear of disclosing food waste volumes. Additionally, the lack of structured market research meant there was limited insight into consumer

acceptance of “ugly” produce, which hindered the development of targeted messaging and engagement strategies. Data sharing also posed a significant obstacle, as companies were often reluctant to share training datasets for the AI model, thereby limiting its adaptability and constraining opportunities for cross-sector deployment. Furthermore, although Spain had passed a national law addressing food loss and waste, there had been no established dialogue between SILL 5 and relevant government bodies to align policies or explore potential support mechanisms.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Several recommendations were made to accelerate SILL 5’s scaling efforts. The team was advised to clarify its governance and exploitation structure by determining whether to form a spin-off, pursue IP licensing, or adopt an open, consortium-led approach. It was considered essential to define roles beyond the project’s end, particularly concerning technical support, system upgrades, and commercialisation responsibilities. Expanding market research was also recommended, with a focus on understanding consumer behaviour and preferences regarding imperfect produce. Aligning the value proposition with broader sustainability trends, retail branding strategies, and emerging regulatory pressures was expected to improve market penetration. Cooperatives were identified as promising first movers, given their scale, technical capacity, and access to funding. SILL 5 was encouraged to engage with local and national governments to explore subsidy opportunities for sustainability-related investments. To address concerns among retailers, it was suggested that the team develop trust-building tools, such as anonymised, aggregated benchmarking data, and frame the technology as an enabler of efficiency and sustainability rather than a compliance mechanism.

The team was also encouraged to standardise integration protocols by developing user-friendly onboarding kits for industrial clients and to document successful case studies such as those from the Andalusian pilots to showcase the technology’s viability. Finally, to mitigate support costs and bridge skill gaps, it was recommended that SILL 5 develop modular, self-paced training materials, including video tutorials, troubleshooting manuals, FAQs, and peer-support platforms. Establishing educational partnerships with agricultural universities and vocational schools was also suggested to create a certification pathway for system operators.

Critical Risks & Mitigations

Several critical risks were identified, alongside strategies to mitigate them. One major concern was low retailer buy-in, which had the potential to significantly limit market access. To address this, SILL 5 was encouraged to develop compelling use cases that demonstrated tangible benefits, such as improvements in yield or reductions in

labour costs, in order to build retailer confidence. Another risk related to the scalability of the solution, as the size and cost of the sorting machine could restrict its applicability across different use cases. To mitigate this, the team was advised to explore the development of smaller, modular versions of the system. Additionally, the absence of a clear post-project path posed a risk to long-term continuity. Without a formal governance framework or a dedicated commercialisation lead, the project risked stagnation after its completion. SILL 5 was therefore urged to formalise its governance structure and clarify its commercialisation strategy to ensure sustainable scaling beyond the ZeroW project.

Figure 8. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 5

SILL 5 demonstrated strong technical readiness and addressed a critical issue in food loss by enabling the utilisation of cosmetically imperfect produce. The potential for both systemic change through strategic partnerships and behavioural shifts via workforce engagement was considerable. However, to fully realise the scalability potential of the technology, immediate attention had been required to formalise governance structures, refine the business model, and build trust with key market stakeholders.

5.1.2.6 SILL 6: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 6, held on 24 April 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological readiness, and market challenges. SILL 6 had focused on scaling their digital sensing and AI solution within the meat industry, aiming to expand its adoption across companies of varying sizes. Their primary approach had been Scaling Up, targeting broader uptake of the solution, while Scaling Down was also under consideration by adapting the models for specific food types or processing lines, such as turkey versus chicken products. Systemic Scaling had been identified as a potential next step as the team worked to deepen industry collaborations and integrate their tools into wider quality assurance systems. The core innovation of their

solution lay in enabling real-time quality control for example, monitoring salt content which supported both operational efficiency and waste reduction.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

SILL 6 had encountered several key challenges during their scaling efforts. Behavioural barriers were evident, as smaller companies were reluctant to adopt digital tools due to perceived complexity and associated costs. On the technical side, the team struggled to access the high-quality sample data necessary for developing and validating their algorithms. Regulatory barriers also posed a significant hurdle; although the solution offered rapid operational insights, it could not substitute for official laboratory-based food safety methods, thereby complicating regulatory compliance.

Recommendations and Next Steps

To advance SILL 6's scaling efforts, several recommendations were made. The team was advised to focus on a licensing model by identifying key targets within their existing industry network and developing materials that clearly communicated the value proposition, highlighting ease of adoption, minimal training requirements, and rapid return on investment. A customised market entry strategy was recommended, involving the creation of two to three "plug-and-play" models tailored to standard meat processing workflows, with differentiated offerings based on company size such as pre-trained models for SMEs and bespoke services for larger processors. To overcome trust and cost-related barriers, SILL 6 was encouraged to offer free demonstrations or temporary licences, as well as simulation data to illustrate predictive accuracy and potential waste reduction benefits. Furthermore, a strong awareness and education strategy might work to remove the reluctance through repetitive marketing campaigns.

They were also advised to pursue public-private funding opportunities, such as Horizon Europe, to support data development for less common processing types, and to collaborate with universities or technology parks to build comprehensive datasets. With regulatory changes on the horizon, the team was encouraged to position their solution as a complement to official food safety methods, particularly in relation to traceability and the anticipated adoption of digital product passports. Finally, SILL 6 was urged to engage in upcoming ZeroW training sessions focused on commercial partnerships and investor readiness, in order to build internal capacity for pitching to both industrial partners and potential licensees.

Risks & Mitigations

Several critical risks were identified during the interview, along with proposed mitigation strategies. To address data access issues for model training, SILL 6 was advised to establish secure R&D partnerships that could facilitate structured data collection. To mitigate reluctance from small companies often stemming from concerns about technological complexity and cost the team was encouraged to develop clear, accessible communication materials that explained the solution's value in simple terms. Additionally, to prevent potential delays in licensing agreements, it was recommended that SILL 6 begin developing the necessary legal framework early, ensuring readiness when commercial opportunities arise.

Figure 9. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 6

SILL 6 demonstrated strong technological readiness, having developed an AI-powered solution for real-time quality control that addressed a critical need within the meat industry. Although their scaling efforts were constrained by behavioural hesitations and technical challenges, the team's focus on licensing, tailored market entry strategies, and the cultivation of strategic partnerships positioned them well to expand their solution across the sector and potentially into adjacent industries. With sustained attention to refining licensing models, securing funding opportunities, and ensuring alignment with regulatory frameworks, SILL 6 was well-placed to scale effectively and contribute to transformative change within the food processing landscape.

5.1.2.7 SILL 7: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 7, held on 21 May 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological readiness, and the challenges they faced. SILL 7 had developed a suite of predictive and prescriptive tools aimed at enhancing decision-making within food banks and among food donors. These tools included a supply chain optimisation model to support resource allocation and improve social impact, dashboards to

predict supply and demand trends while suggesting appropriate donation strategies, and a decision support system adopted by retailers to monitor food waste and identify donation potential. The tools had been tested and implemented in collaboration with the Dutch national food bank organisation (Voedselbanken Nederland), individual food banks, and a national retailer. SILL 7's scaling approach had been predominantly non-commercial and impact driven. They focused on scaling up by refining their tools and embedding them more deeply into the operations of existing partners, particularly the national retailer and food bank network. In parallel, they pursued scaling deep by aiming to change internal practices, enhance data awareness, and shift behaviours within existing systems. Systemic scaling was also considered, as the team recognised the potential of their tools to support broader structural change through collaboration with national food donation and retail systems. However, the team was not pursuing commercial scaling or productisation, and they had no ambitions to become a service provider or implementer beyond the scope of the research project.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

Several key barriers had been identified during the interview. While the dashboards were technically flexible and adaptable to other retailers and food bank systems, differences in data infrastructure and standardisation across organisations posed significant challenges to replication. A plug-and-play model was not feasible, and each implementation required customisation and close collaboration. The team demonstrated strong capabilities in research, tool design, and development, but lacked the interest or internal capacity to independently scale implementation. Full-scale deployment would have required the involvement of consultancy firms with IT and data integration expertise. In terms of governance and ownership, the tools were handed over to participating organisations such as retailers and food banks for continued use.

However, no independent governance model or spin-off structure had been planned, and much of the implementation remained reliant on local volunteer capacity, particularly within food banks. On the policy and legal front, tax incentives for food donations in the Netherlands were being phased out. Although cost savings and social impact continued to motivate food donations, collaboration with the government on this issue was minimal, especially compared to more active policy environments in countries like Spain and Portugal.

Recommendations and Next Steps

The following recommendations had been made to enhance SILL 7's scaling efforts. First, the team was advised to consolidate their impact at the national level by

deepening engagement with key partners, such as Voedselbanken Nederland and the headquarters of the participating retailer, to ensure that the tools were institutionalised and kept up to date. They were also encouraged to provide clear documentation and training materials to support onboarding of new volunteers and future implementation efforts. In addition, SILL 7 was advised to support broader ecosystem learning by finalising and distributing the planned handbook on food bank innovations and tool-related insights.

Collaboration with European food bank networks was recommended to explore opportunities for tool replication or methodological adaptation in other countries. SILL 7 had demonstrated promising results with its suite of tools, which were designed to improve food bank operations and enhance decision-making in food donation processes. While their scaling ambitions remained non-commercial, the team showed strong potential to expand their impact by strengthening national partnerships and fostering wider European collaboration. Their tools had already shown early success, particularly in increasing donation volumes and operational efficiency, positioning them to contribute meaningfully to systemic change in the food waste and donation landscape.

5.1.2.8 SILL 8: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the 1:1 interview with SILL 8, held on April 17, 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological feasibility, and market challenges. SILL 8 aimed to repurpose unsellable food waste from retail stores through on-site dehydration. The resulting residue was used as a substrate for growing mycological microalgae or fungi, contributing to waste reduction, circular economy principles, and biomass production, potentially for food or other bio-based applications.

SILL 8 positioned itself within multiple scaling pathways. In the short term, they focused on immediate scaling-up, as the process was ready to scale in terms of machinery, logistics, and cultivation. However, the economic feasibility still required validation, and a cost-benefit analysis was planned to compare the dehydration and cultivation process with alternative waste processing methods such as composting or anaerobic digestion. In the medium term, their scaling-out strategy involved replicating the process in additional SONAE (Continente) stores or through partnerships with other retailers. Pilots were planned across different store profiles such as urban versus rural locations to test the system's adaptability and document compatibility with additional waste streams. Looking toward the long term, SILL 8 aimed to achieve scaling-deep by influencing consumer acceptance and regulatory frameworks. This would involve transitioning from a proof-of-concept model to an accepted bio-based production method through public communication campaigns, certification pilots, and regulatory engagement.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

During the interview, several key barriers and challenges were identified. One major issue was related to market entry regulations. Certification hurdles for food or cosmetic applications, particularly due to the substrate's origin in food waste, posed a significant constraint. Although the dehydration process met technical standards, it was not officially certified as an "appropriate" method for handling animal by-products safely, especially in Portugal, limiting its application scope. Another challenge was consumer perception. There was notable scepticism surrounding products such as algae that were grown on a food waste substrate, which negatively impacted their marketability, particularly within the food sector.

Finally, strategic uncertainty emerged as a constraint. The retailer SONAE had not yet committed to scaling the process across multiple stores. This hesitation may have been due to concerns about costs, energy consumption, or other competing priorities related to waste reduction.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Several recommendations were made to enhance SILL 8's scaling efforts. The team was advised to complete a cost-benefit analysis comparing the dehydration and cultivation processes with alternative waste processing methods such as composting or anaerobic digestion. They were encouraged to engage proactively with SONAE decision-makers by presenting the project's results, potential savings, and the brand value it could generate in terms of corporate social responsibility, while also aligning with relevant regulatory pressures. Expansion into other geographic and contextual settings was recommended, including replicating the process in additional SONAE stores or partnering with other retailers. It was suggested that machinery size and logistics plans be adjusted based on each store's throughput. SILL 8 was also encouraged to broaden the types of waste streams tested for compatibility and economic viability, with particular focus on bakery waste, fruit peels, and other organic materials. They had already experimented with various food categories and considered the texture of the resulting residue, for instance, sugar-rich foods tended to harden and could not be properly homogenised in the dehydrator.

To support more transformative, systemic change, SILL 8 was advised to prioritise efforts that would influence consumer acceptance and regulatory alignment. This involved engaging with certification bodies to explore possible exceptions and documenting results through pilot programmes. Public communication campaigns were also recommended, potentially in collaboration with NGOs or using EU dissemination platforms, in order to help normalise the idea of growing algae on food waste.

Looking beyond the ZeroW project, SILL 8 was encouraged to engage with retail strategists and continue discussions with SONAE leadership to identify and respond to any emerging strategic interests. Drafting a post-project scaling roadmap was also recommended, outlining technical milestones, cost-saving targets, and the certification requirements needed for market entry. Close attention to upcoming EU policies was advised, particularly in areas such as food waste valorisation, the circular economy, and certification for bio-based products.

Finally, the team was encouraged to develop a Business Model Canvas to map their value proposition, customer segments, key resources, and potential revenue streams. They were also advised to model the environmental and economic impacts of their process at multiple levels—local, regional, and national—to support strategic planning and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 10. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 8

SILL 8 demonstrated a strong proof of concept and technical feasibility in repurposing food waste for fungal and algae cultivation. While they faced market entry barriers, regulatory hurdles, and consumer perception challenges, they were positioned well for future scaling. With further validation of economic feasibility, proactive engagement with retailers, and alignment with policy developments, SILL 8 had the potential to become a commercially viable solution with significant environmental impact.

5.1.2.9 SILL 9: Scaling Strategy and Key Insights

In the one-on-one interview with SILL 9, held on April 17, 2025, the team discussed their scaling strategy, technological feasibility, and the market challenges they faced. SILL 9 had focused on developing digital interventions aimed at improving consumer food planning and reducing household-level food waste. The primary innovations in

development included a behavioural label that incorporated environmental and waste-related metrics, as well as a smart meal planning tool designed to guide consumers toward more sustainable food consumption patterns. Both tools were supported by scientific modelling and validated through field-tested datasets. SILL 9 had positioned itself within multiple scaling pathways. Their primary focus was on scaling deep, aiming to improve the quality of impact and integration within the target communities. As a secondary consideration, they explored scaling out by replicating their approach in other countries, depending on the availability of relevant data and demonstrated interest. However, systemic scaling remained limited due to a lack of political or institutional engagement at a broader scale. Rather than prioritising conventional scaling methods, SILL 9 followed the Scaling Social Entrepreneurial Impact framework outlined in WP6 to guide their approach to scaling societal impact.

Challenges and Bottlenecks

During the interview, several key barriers were identified. Data availability across countries had been a significant limiting factor, particularly concerning consumer food waste behaviour, product pack sizes, recipe databases, and price information. The team possessed strong academic expertise but faced limited organisational capacity, lacking the internal resources necessary for software deployment, stakeholder engagement, and scaling the implementation of their tools. Additionally, legal and practical restrictions had prevented university researchers from directly advocating for policy adoption or commercial implementation. Although early contact had been made with national consumer food agencies and other institutional actors, stakeholder engagement remained ad hoc and was constrained by resource limitations.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Several strategic recommendations were made to enhance SILL 9's scaling efforts. The team was advised to formalise and publish a replication protocol by developing clear documentation and replication guides for both the behavioural label and the meal planning tool. These guides were expected to include minimal data requirements and be designed for use by technical professionals or public bodies.

It was recommended that SILL 9 target institutional partnerships to support uptake, with direct engagement suggested for food consumer agencies such as health or sustainability authorities. This engagement aimed to explore opportunities for integration into national guidance tools. Scientific publications and open-access datasets were proposed as means to build credibility and reduce barriers for future adoption.

The team was encouraged to enable limited external replication by creating a modular software prototype that could be transferred to external developers for adaptation. Collaboration with digital innovation hubs or public sector IT teams in other EU Member States was identified as a potential pathway to support this process. Finally, SILL 9 was advised to prepare for public communication and impact demonstration by strengthening the narrative around the tool's expected social impact. This included highlighting how the tools influenced consumer behaviour, the anticipated environmental outcomes, and the population segments most likely to benefit.

Figure 11. ZeroW Scaling Strategies 1-1 Interview: SILL 9

SILL 9 contributed significantly to ZeroW's objectives on consumer-level food waste reduction and behavioural change. While their scaling ambitions differed from other SILLs, their structured approach to knowledge dissemination and methodological rigor positioned them as a replicable social innovation with long-term potential impact in public policy and sustainability programming.

5.1.3 Capacity Building Activities

To address the unique needs and challenges identified by each SILL, joint capacity-building activities were organised to develop the skills and knowledge critical for securing funding and fostering sustainable growth. These activities brought together all SILLs to focus on key areas such as understanding how to approach investors, navigating the public funding landscape, and strengthening their ability to secure resources for long-term sustainability. The sessions were designed to address common challenges while also offering tailored support based on the individual requirements of each SILL.

Workshops and group exercises focused on crafting a compelling investor pitch, equipping SILLs with the skills needed to engage effectively with potential investors by developing clear, compelling, and well-targeted investment pitches. These sessions covered the key elements of a successful pitch, including the value proposition, scalability, and market need. Through hands-on activities, participants developed and refined their pitches, with some preparing for the Pitching Session with Investors at the ZeroW Final Event. Peer feedback and role-playing exercises helped the teams practice delivering their pitches with confidence.

On October 16, 2025, F6S delivered the final training session titled “Building a Sustainable Funding Strategy”, which was open to all ZeroW consortium members and particularly aimed at the SILLs. The session focused on practical approaches to developing long-term financial strategies to support the scaling and sustainability of innovation beyond the project's lifetime. The workshop was delivered by Filipe Neves from F6S and provided participants with useful insights into funding models, financial planning, and strategic thinking. It supported the SILLs in reflecting on their existing approaches and considering new ways to secure future resources. The session was well-received and contributed to strengthening the SILLs’ capacity to plan for financial sustainability in a post-project context.

Figure 12. ZeroW Building a Sustainable Funding Strategy Session

The training emphasised the importance of both public and private funding as critical tools for scaling and sustainability. SILLs learned how to leverage public funding, such as government grants and EU development funds, by aligning their projects with relevant funding priorities. They also explored approaches to securing private funding from sources like venture capital and impact investors. These topics were integrated

into the workshop, equipping participants to strategically utilise both funding avenues to accelerate scaling and maintain financial sustainability.

In summary, a varied approach to capacity-building activities, through targeted training and mentoring, was employed to equip SILLs with the skills, insights, and resources needed to scale their innovations effectively. This ensured that they were prepared to meet the challenges of scaling in diverse regional contexts and could drive long-term, sustainable impact.

5.2 SILL Pitching Session with Investor at the ZeroW Final Event

In the lead-up to the final event, SILLs were supported through a comprehensive series of preparatory activities designed to fine-tune their pitching skills and refine their investment proposals. These activities included pitch coaching sessions where SILLs received personalised feedback on effectively communicating the value proposition, scalability, and impact of their innovations. SILLs were guided on tailoring their presentations to address the specific interests and priorities of the investor attending the event. F6S also provided training on how to craft compelling narratives that resonated with different types of investors, ensuring that the teams were equipped to engage diverse stakeholders effectively.

Figure 13. ZeroW Pitching Session: Presentation from SILL 1

These preparations were reinforced when the investor, proactively shared a set of specific tips and guidance with the SILLs. This direct input was aimed at helping the teams effectively communicate their value proposition, scalability, and impact, ensuring their pitches addressed the investor's specific priorities.

The final pitching session took place on September 16th and served as a crucial platform for the SILLs to present their solutions. The session was moderated by F6S

and featured Arne Hautekitet from Astanor Ventures as the sole investor and assessor. A total of eight SILLs (SILL 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, and 9) presented their solutions.

Figure 14. ZeroW Pitching Session: Presentation from SILL 5

The core objective of the session was to gather an assessment of the SILLs' investment readiness. Each SILL was allocated a concise, high-pressure format: five minutes for the presentation followed by three minutes for questions from the investor and the audience. F6S successfully guided the event, keeping time and encouraging productive dialogue. The investor evaluated each SILL across ten key criteria, focusing on clarity, innovation, market opportunity, team performance, and business viability.

Figure 15. ZeroW Pitching Session: Presentation from SILL 3

The intensive, eight-pitch session successfully marked the culmination of the ZeroW project, providing the SILLs with invaluable high-stakes experience and direct feedback from a leading venture capital firm focused on systemic impact.

6 Monitoring and Evaluation of Scaling Efforts

To track the effectiveness of scaling strategies in Task 6.3, F6S proposed a set of KPIs and metrics that allowed measuring progress and the overall impact. These self-imposed KPIs ensured that strategies for stimulating investment in FLW reduction innovations produced the desired outcomes across different regions. Table 4 showed the proposed KPIs and associated metrics:

Table 4. Scaling Strategies and Activities Proposed KPIs

KPI Group	KPI Metrics
Engagement of SILLs in Scaling Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ KPI #1: Number of SILLs participating in scaling strategy development: >5 ▪ KPI #2: Number of SILLs that have developed a formal scaling plan: >5 ▪ KPI #3: Number of 1-1 interviews and mentoring sessions conducted: >10 ▪ KPI #4: Number of innovations shortlisted for investor pitch events: >5
Investor & Corporate Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ KPI #5: Number of investors or corporate entities contacted: >20 ▪ KPI #6: Number of investors or corporates attending pitch sessions: >2 ▪ KPI #7: Number of identified and promoted opportunities to connect with investors & public funding: >5
Capacity Building and Training Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ KPI #8: Number of capacity building sessions provided to SILLs on scaling and investment readiness: >3 ▪ KPI #9: Number of SILLs participating in training sessions: >5 ▪ KPI #10: Investor or corporate satisfaction score: >4

Feedback loops were essential for monitoring the progress of scaling strategies and ensuring continuous improvement based on real-time data and stakeholder input. In the context of scaling innovations within SILLs, these loops created a dynamic process where strategies were not only implemented but also constantly refined based on the evolving needs of the market, stakeholders, and investors.

7 Conclusions and Future Directions

This deliverable outlined a comprehensive approach for scaling innovations developed within SILLs of the ZeroW project. It focused on creating SILL- and region-specific strategies to stimulate investment and promote the adoption of FLW reduction innovations. The work centred on understanding the unique challenges in each of the three macro-regions involved in the project, providing tailored support to innovators, and fostering connections between SILLs, investors, corporates, and public entities.

The development of region-specific scaling strategies was a key project milestone that was achieved by the successful submission of this version of the deliverable, and verification by regional stakeholders. One of the main findings was that regional differences in market readiness, investment ecosystems, and regulatory frameworks required customised scaling strategies.

Rather than employing a universal approach, the strategy acknowledged these variations and aimed to support SILLs with regionally specific solutions. Activities such as training and mentoring were critical for enhancing SILLs' capacity to scale their innovations, improving their understanding of investor expectations, and refining their pitching skills.

The ZeroW project emphasised the importance of building connections with potential investors, leveraging internal networks and project channels to promote investment opportunities and facilitate SILLs' market entry. Capacity-building activities included targeted workshops and mentoring sessions, helping SILLs identify scalable innovations and develop stronger business cases. The initial strategies presented in this deliverable aimed to ensure that SILLs were prepared to enter the market and attract the necessary investment to grow.

By M45, when the ZeroW Final Event took place, these efforts were showcased in a high-profile pitching session. The path forward included refining these strategies based on ongoing feedback and preparing for the submission of the final deliverable in M46. The end goal was to create a sustainable ecosystem where SILL innovations could thrive, supported by a robust network of public and private stakeholders dedicated to reducing food loss and waste across Europe.

Appendix I: ZeroW Scaling Strategies Questionnaire Answers

18. If yes, what types of partnerships would be most beneficial for scaling?

● Regional government agencies	4
● Local or international corporates	3
● Universities and research institutions	2
● Non-profits or NGOs	0
● Other	1

19. Would you be open to collaborating with other SILLs in your region to overcome common scaling challenges?

● Yes	7
● No	2

20. If yes, what types of collaborations would you find most beneficial?

● Joint market entry strategies	3
● Resource sharing	4
● Joint investor outreach	4
● Shared training programmes	3
● Other	1

21. Are you currently part of any networks or ecosystems that support innovation scaling?

● Yes	5
● No	4

